

The effectiveness of the student teams' achievement divisions in social studies learning on activeness and learning outcomes

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ABSTRACT

Student teams' achievement divisions (STAD) is a learning method that can provide active responses to students so that learning is maximized, but this method is still very rarely used by social studies teachers, thus making social studies learning less than optimal. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of the question students have method in social studies learning to increase student activity and learning outcomes. The procedure divides two class groups experimental and control using a quasi-experimental nonequivalent control group design. A sample of 122 seventh-grade kids from a junior high school in Yogyakarta was utilized as the population. While instruments, interviews, and observations were employed in the data collecting process, cluster random sampling was the sampling strategy. An N-gain score test and an independent sample T-test were utilized in the data analysis. The findings demonstrated that, when compared to traditional classroom settings, the STAD's social studies teaching methodology was able to improve student engagement and learning outcomes. The N-gain score test was classified as medium, and the independent sample T-test yielded a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the STAD approach has a huge influence, which makes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Instructors of social studies have not employed a variety of techniques in the context of junior high school instruction. As a result, the prevalent teaching strategies continue to be classical, which may contribute to the poor learning outcomes and quality. This demonstrates how Indonesian education quality is still below par with that of other nations [1]–[5]. In order to meet this challenge and raise the standard of instruction, the teacher's involvement is crucial. In order for pupils to grasp the content being presented, teachers should take an active part in their job as professionals in education and demonstrate originality and innovation in the techniques they choose to teach. To accomplish the intended learning objectives, teachers

must use teaching strategies that are appropriate for the lesson's subject matter [6]–[8]. Achieving learning outcomes is one of the learning objectives, according to Bolinger and Warren [9]. The accomplishment of student learning outcomes serves as a gauge for the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. The relationship between educators and students is critical to achieving this achievement [10], [11]. In order to increase student activity and learning outcomes, teachers must be able to select and use appropriate teaching strategies based on the characteristics of their student [12], [13].

In order to impart knowledge, develop skills, and assist students in their learning, teachers play a critical role in the social studies curriculum [14]–[16]. Thus, for the learning process to be successful and efficient, teachers must possess the necessary credentials and competences. Students will find it simpler to absorb and digest the content being taught if there is a strong interest in their education and an effective teaching strategy is used. The growth of student learning outcomes is also significantly influenced by the teaching methodology employed in classrooms [17], [18].

Low student learning results and a lack of enthusiasm in the learning process might be caused by inappropriate teaching strategies [19]. One-way and passive learning approaches that are disconnected from students' everyday lives are frequently the root cause of learning techniques' inaccuracies [20], [21]. Students do not comprehend the content being taught by the teacher as a result of their fear and anxiety about asking questions [22], [23]. Even if they are confused by the instruction, students might not be confident enough to ask questions. Students have questions to ask, but these obstacles prevent them from actively posing them. Teachers and students don't engage or provide feedback to one another as a result of this passive attitude [24], [25].

The issue of classroom management is the root cause of this predicament. Since the goal of class management is to enable students to work in an organized way in order to effectively and efficiently accomplish learning objectives [26], [27]. Teachers must be able to make an effort to improve by being aware of these factors. This includes selecting a teaching strategy that will enhance social studies learning outcomes and facilitate the success of the teaching and learning process [28], [29]. The student teams' achievement divisions (STAD) learning approach is one of the teaching strategies that can boost student engagement and academic results [30]. STAD learning method is a learning method that organizes students into small teams, where each team member has the responsibility to learn and achieve achievements together [8], [31], [32]. This method can be implemented in learning social studies which allows students to work together, discuss, and collaborate in understanding social, economic, and political concepts.

The STAD learning technique is a cooperative learning strategy that uses group cooperation to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes [33]. Students are placed in small groups with individuals who have different skill levels using the STAD approach [34], [35]. Each group has four to six members, allowing for intense interaction between students. During the learning process, group members work together to achieve the set learning goals [36], [37].

Previous research [38]–[40] explains that STAD because it can foster collaborative experiences and increase group responsibility, the learning method used in social studies instruction can have a positive effect on students' learning outcomes and keep them actively engaged in the learning process. This method also encourages students to get the most out of their social studies education by using the material related to Indonesia's declaration of independence. It may be anticipated that STAD can assist learning activities and create the ideal environment through the learning technique, allowing students to reach their full potential in line with the established learning and education goals. Thus, the goal of this study was to examine how the STAD learning approach may be used to improve learning outcomes and student engagement.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Table 1 illustrates the quasi-experimental design of this study, which employs a quantitative methodology and splits participants into two class groups. aiming to evaluate the efficacy of the STAD approach in social studies instruction in order to boost student engagement and academic results [41]. Because it eliminates the need for complete randomization and gives the researcher control over the variables influencing study outcomes, the quasi-experimental design was selected. The experimental and control groups were given a pretest (O1) to begin this investigation. A posttest (O2) was then given to both groups; the experimental group was treated (X) using STAD-based learning techniques, while the control group used traditional learning models [42].

Table 1. Quasi-experimental quantitative research design

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O1	X	O2

2.1. Population, sample, and sampling technique

A sample of 119 students from state Junior High School 2 Sleman in Yogyakarta, who were in the seventh grade, were utilized as the population. By splitting the sample into many distinct groups (clusters), the sampling strategy employed cluster random sampling [43]. The sample is determined by dividing it into two class groups: the control class (conventional or not provided treatment) and the experimental class (treatment given). The group must take a pretest and posttest before receiving therapy; this will allow for an analysis of the differences in the two groups' changes.

2.2. Measuring instrument

This study used observation data collection techniques, interviews, and tests. Observations and interviews are used to analyze research needs related to social studies learning. While the test instrument is used to measure student activity variables in the learning process and measure student learning outcomes. With fifteen statements aimed at both instructors and students, the questionnaire seeks feedback on how animated movies are used in the classroom. These metrics center on student engagement, active involvement in class discussions, group cooperation, and the use of supplemental learning materials [44], [45]. Furthermore, comprehension of social studies topics, analytical and critical thinking skills, and presenting and communication abilities are also variables linked to social studies learning outcomes [46], [47]. The questionnaire presents individual attributes, such as knowledge, attitudes, and talents, using a five-point Likert scale to generate a score or value.

2.3. Data analysis

In order to investigate population parameter-related hypotheses, this study analyzes data using parametric statistical techniques. In order to assess the efficacy of the STAD technique in social studies education and to improve student engagement and learning outcomes, researchers can utilize the IBM SPSS 25 statistics program to analyze study data and apply the N-gain test. Descriptive analysis and precondition testing are done first to make sure the data satisfies the requirements before testing the hypothesis. The tests for homogeneity and normalcy make up the requirement. To determine if the data were normal, we employed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov model with a significance threshold of $p > 0.05$. use the One-Way Anova model, Levene's evaluate, and a significance threshold of $p > 0.05$ to evaluate homogeneity. Additionally, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ will be used to examine significant differences between the two class groups using an independent sample T-test. Additionally, taking into account the markers of the distribution of N-gain scores, the study of the N-gain score test aims to explain the capacity of student learning outcomes. An N-gain score of more than 0.7 ($g > 0.7$) is regarded as strong and denotes a notable improvement in learning outcomes. The N-gain score is deemed moderate if it falls between 0.3 and 0.7 ($0.3 \leq g < 0.7$), suggesting a little improvement in learning outcomes compared to the high group [48]. In the meanwhile, it is regarded as poor in the area of improving learning outcomes if the N-gain score is less than 0.3 ($g < 0.3$). Distribution of N-gain scores as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of N-gain scores

N-gain value	Criteria
$g > 0.7$	High
$0.3 \leq g < 0.7$	Medium
$g < 0.3$	Low

3. RESULTS

3.1. Descriptive of statistical analysis

Based on the results of the average scores obtained from the two class groups, there are differences, which means that the implementation of STAD as a method in social studies learning is to increase student activity and learning outcomes. Table 3 describes the statistical analysis of the number of samples is 119 with details of 87 experimental classes and 32 control classes. The average score of the experimental class was 69.05 pretest and 87.10 posttest, while the average score of the control class was 62.06 pretest and 79.27 posttests.

Table 3. Statistical description

Class	N	Descriptive statistics			
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
Pretest experiment	87	53.00	84.00	69.0562	9.38263
Posttest experiment	87	52.00	92.00	87.1090	8.13526
Pretest control	32	57.00	78.00	62.0625	9.45996
Posttest control	32	64.00	81.00	79.2732	7.51939
Valid N (listwise)	32				

3.2. Pre-requisite analysis test

To ascertain whether or not the hypothesis testing can proceed, a precondition test is carried out. Data variance necessitates homogenous groups being compared and data from a regularly distributed population. The normality test employed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov path model, while the homogeneity test used one-way ANOVA for the analysis of variance of the precondition test data.

3.2.1. Normality test

The purpose of the normalcy test is to determine whether or not the observed data has a normal distribution. This is significant because a lot of parametric statistical techniques, such regression analysis and parametric hypothesis testing, depend on the assumption that the data is normally distributed. We can ascertain if the proper statistical procedure is applied in the data analysis by checking the normalcy of the data. The findings of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov model-based normalcy test study are shown in Table 4. According to the results, the experimental class group scored significantly higher 0.178 compared to 0.192 for the control class group. These results indicate that the data from both groups have a normal distribution, as seen by the values obtained for significance level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4. Normality test results

Class	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Description
	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Experiment	.412	87	.178	Normal
Control	.521	32	.192	Normal

3.2.2. Homogeneity test

Based on the findings presented in Table 5, the results of the homogeneity test conducted on the control class and experimental class revealed a significance value of 0.149. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the variances of the two groups being compared. Consequently, it can be concluded that the control class and experimental class are homogeneous, as the obtained significance value for both classes is greater than the predetermined significance level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). The homogeneity test is essential in research as it assesses the similarity of variances between groups. When conducting comparative analyses or hypothesis testing, it is important to ensure that the groups being compared have similar variances to maintain the validity and reliability of the statistical tests employed. In this case, the homogeneity test results confirm that there is no significant disparity in the variances between the control class and experimental class, providing a solid foundation for further comparative analyses and conclusions drawn from the data.

Table 5. Homogeneity test results

Class	Test of homogeneity of variances				Description
	Levene's Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.	
Experiment and control	3.689	1	119	.149	Homogen

3.3. Hypothesis testing analysis with independent samples T-test and N-gain score

Based on the output provided in Table 6, the results of the independent sample T-test indicated a significant difference between the experimental class and the control class. The Sig. (2-tailed) value obtained from the T-test analysis was 0.000, which is less than the predetermined significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). This implies that there is a statistically significant difference in the average scores of student learning outcomes between the two groups specifically, the group using STAD method in social studies learning and the group utilizing conventional learning methods. The significant difference observed in the average scores suggests that STAD method has a noticeable impact on student learning outcomes in social studies when compared to conventional teaching approaches. The findings indicate that STAD method enhances students' understanding, analytical skills, critical thinking abilities, and presentation and communication skills in the context of social studies.

The results of the independent sample T-test are further supported by the N-gain scores, as presented in Table 7. These scores demonstrate the effectiveness of implementing STAD method in social studies learning, as they indicate an increase in both student activity and learning outcomes. Table 7 displays the N-gain scores, which represent the difference between the posttest scores and the pretest scores for both the experimental class and the control class. The N-gain score is a valuable indicator of the degree of improvement or growth experienced by the students in their learning outcomes. Upon examination of Table 7, it becomes evident that the N-gain scores for the experimental class, where STAD method was implemented, are higher compared to those of the control class. This signifies a greater improvement in student learning outcomes in the experimental class because of utilizing STAD method.

Table 6. Test results of independent sample T-test

Result	Independent samples test								
	Levene's test for equality of variances		T-test for equality of means						
	F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	1.133	.323	3.971	121	.000	6.27363	1.98273	3.38297	9.57262
Equal variances not assumed			4.105	62.943	.000	6.27363	1.98273	3.12361	9.42516

Table 7. N-gain score test results

Class	N-gain score	Criteria
Experiment 1	0.5	Medium
Experiment 2	0.5	Medium
Experiment 3	0.3	Medium
Control	0.2	Low

The output results of Table 7 show that the N-gain values obtained from the experimental classes 1, 2, and 3 are 0.5 and 0.3 with a level (0.3 g 0.7) which is categorized as medium. The N-gain score from the control class was 0.2 with a level ($g < 0.3$) in the low category. The results of the N-gain score analysis have shown that there is a significant increase in the gain from the average test score of the experimental class with the control class. The results of the average pretest experimental class 1 were 76.08 and posttest 86.22, experiment 2 pretest 71.67, and posttest 83.89. Experiment 3 pretest 61.33 and posttest 81.79, while the average score for the control class pretest is 61.0 and posttest is 78.38. Thus, the results of the N-gain score have provided an explanation that the use of STAD a method in social studies learning is proven to increase student activity and learning outcomes.

4. DISCUSSION

Social studies learning, which includes developments and changes in the earth related to the concepts of space and time, is often carried out thematically and theoretically with an emphasis on memorization. This causes many students to consider history lessons easy. The current learning process is more focused on achieving material targets and less on guiding in understanding concepts to students, especially in history social studies learning. In class, learning activities are dominated by the teacher's lecture method, with students just sitting, taking notes, and listening. This limitation of interaction causes the learning atmosphere to be not conducive and students to become passive so that learning outcomes become less than optimal. Therefore, we need a new learning method that can increase student activity and learning outcomes.

This is to the theory of Widiastuti *et al.* [49] which states that the success factor is one of the factors that influence student learning outcomes. Learning success will be achieved if students feel able to carry out the desired activities and feel satisfaction in doing so. In addition, the performance of teachers who can provide direction and become good facilitators also influences student success [50], [51]. Thus, students will be motivated to take part in the historical social studies learning process by using active methods, such as STAD as their learning model [52].

Education is one of the important factors in the formation of competent and knowledgeable future generations. Therefore, the development of effective learning methods is a major concern in increasing student activity and learning outcomes [53], [54]. One method that can be used in the social studies learning context is STAD method [55]. The STAD method is a cooperative approach that involves working together in groups to achieve learning goals [56]. This method involves forming small teams in class, where each member of the team has an active role in achieving common learning goals [57]. In social studies learning, the STAD method can provide many benefits, including increasing student activity and learning outcomes.

Previous research [58], [59] explained that STAD in learning can increase activity and learning outcomes by involving students in teamwork. This method encourages active participation, collaboration, deeper understanding, and development of students' social skills. STAD is the right method to currently apply in social studies learning so that student involvement and optimal learning outcomes can be the focus, the STAD method offers an interesting approach and has the potential to bring about positive changes in social studies learning [60], [61]. However, it is important to remember that implementing this method requires careful preparation, balanced group arrangements, careful teacher monitoring, and the use of appropriate evaluation instruments to objectively measure student engagement and learning outcomes.

STAD method can be used as an alternative to choosing the model or method used by teachers to increase activeness and learning outcomes in learning social studies [62]. In a lively atmosphere, students engage in small group discussions that encourage collaboration and joint problem-solving. They are not only passive listeners but

also key actors in understanding complex IPS concepts and applying complex social studies knowledge [63], [64]. Through close interaction and cooperation, students feel the urge to contribute to their full potential within their team, creating a strong sense of responsibility and accountability. In addition, the use of STAD also stimulates emotional involvement, arouses interest, and strengthens students' motivation in achieving joint success. Thus, STAD not only provides a pleasant learning experience but also ensures optimal learning outcomes in social studies learning.

5. CONCLUSION

The implementation of STAD method in social studies learning based on the results of the analysis of hypothesis testing in this study was declared effective on student activity and learning outcomes. This is based on the results of the independent sample T-test with the acquisition of a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so there is a significant difference between the experimental class using STAD method and the control class (conventional). Confirmed by the results of the N-gain score test, which is included in the medium category, with the intention that STAD method in social studies learning can respond to activeness and improve student learning outcomes. The general implication of this research is that it can be used as a support for other research on similar themes, especially social studies learning design. Practically it can be used as an alternative by teachers to use STAD method in social studies learning so that it is more effective and maximal in achieving learning goals so that social studies learning will remain of high quality in improving students' competencies, abilities and skills. In addition, the use of the STAD method in social studies learning has a positive impact on increasing collaboration, student involvement, responsibility, social skills, and motivation in social studies learning. This helps students gain a better understanding of social studies concepts and develop skills that are relevant in social studies contexts.

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